

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 26 May – 4 June 2024

Report published: March 2025

**Scandinavian brown bears:
Winter den sites and feeding ecology
of bears in the woodlands of Dalarna
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**Authors:
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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

2024 was the fourth year of Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists assisting the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021), 2022 and 2023. It was the second year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days. Citizen scientists collected data on bear denning behaviour and feeding ecology by investigating den sites and by collecting fresh scats from day bed sites of GPS-collared brown bears.

The expedition ran from 26 May to 4 June 2024 and investigated 29 winter bear den sites of 27 different bears. All sites explored were initially recorded during the winter of 2023/2024, with two exceptions: one den used in the previous winter 2022/2023 and one very old den used in 2013/2014. Additionally, two bears changed dens at least once during the hibernation period, although only one of the second dens was located. A particularly unusual finding was the discovery of two 1.5-year-old male bears sharing a den, which had only occurred once in the last 40 years in the SBBRP dataset — when two 1.5-year-old female bears also shared a den.

Out of the 29 positions identified, 27 were confirmed as actual bear dens. The types of dens found included 5 anthill dens, 8 soil dens, 6 anthill/soil hybrid dens, 5 rock dens and 3 basket dens, with no dens found under uprooted trees. Two pregnant females gave birth during winter while hibernating in basket dens, which are typically used by larger males, not females. Notably, all dens were constructed within the core areas of the bears' home ranges, rather than on the periphery.

A preliminary analysis of the SBBRP's long-term data set (1987-2024) revealed notable trends. Solitary male bears preferred open dens (32%) compared to females (12%) and females with cubs (13%). Excavated dens were the most common den type across all bear categories, constituting 58-77%. The selection of den types has evolved over the years, with increased use of open and natural dens, especially by females with cubs. Whether this shift is due to climate change, individual behaviour, human impact or other factors is yet to be determined and will be explored in future studies.

The expedition also collected three post-hibernation bear scats at the den sites, which were packed, labelled, and frozen for future analysis. Evidence of cubs, including climbing marks, scats and small day beds, was found at five den sites. The habitat surrounding the dens was dominated by older forests, primarily Scots pine (52%), followed by spruce (27%) and birches (21%). None of the dens were located in wetland areas such as bogs or swamps, and most were situated on slopes, with only a few on flat ground. The trees surrounding the dens had an average height of around 3 metres.

The expedition found 31 scats at cluster positions, with only one cluster site revealing the remains of an adult moose kill, which may indicate a decrease in the moose population in Sweden and the study area. In previous years, kill remains were found at about every fourth cluster. Remarkably, during its 10-day research period, the expedition was able to collect 100% of the scat samples that the SBBRP typically collects in a year.

The citizen scientists' contributions were invaluable in helping the SBBRP meet its data collection goals. The continuous support from Biosphere Expeditions is crucial for these long-term research projects, as extensive datasets accumulated over many years are required to draw robust scientific conclusions.

Due to the high turnover of marked bears, mainly because of significantly increased hunting activity, the SBBRP faces challenges in maintaining an adequate number of collared bears for research. In 2024, the number of marked individuals was reduced by 50% due to hunting, requiring the capture of 20–40 new bears. Capturing and collaring new bears is costly, labour-intensive and complicated. For this reason, new bear capture methods using camera traps will be developed in 2025, and assisting with this will be a new task for the expedition in 2025.

Overall, the expedition's findings and the ongoing support from citizen scientists and Biosphere Expeditions significantly contribute to the SBBRP's mission of understanding brown bear behaviour and ensuring the conservation of these magnificent animals.

Sammandrag

2024 var det fjärde året som expeditionsdeltagare från Biosphere Expeditions assisterade det Skandinaviska Björnprojektet (SBBRP) efter 2019 (följt av ett COVID-19-relaterat uppehåll 2020 och 2021) samt 2022 och 2023. Det var det andra året då fältarbetet förlängdes med två dagar till totalt tio dagars expedition. Expeditionsdeltagare samlade in data om björnarnas vinterbeteende och födointag genom att undersöka idesplatser och samla in färska björnspilling från daglegor från GPS-märkta brunbjörnar. Expeditionen, som genomfördes från den 26 maj till den 4 juni 2024, undersökte 29 iden från 27 olika björnar. Alla de undersökta idespositionerna registrerades ursprungligen under vintern 2023/2024, med två undantag: ett ide som användes föregående vinter (2022/2023) och ett mycket gammalt ide från 2013/2014. Dessutom bytte två björnar iden minst en gång under vintersömn, men endast ett av de andra vinteride hittades. Ett särskilt ovanligt fynd var upptäckten av två 1,5-åriga hanbjörnar som delade sitt vinteride, något som bara observerats en gång under de senaste 40 åren i SBBRP:s data – då två 1,5-åriga honbjörnar delade ett ide.

Av de 29 identifierade positionerna bekräftades 27 som verkliga björniden. De idestyper som hittades inkluderade 5 myrstackide, 8 jordide, 6 myrstack/jordide, 5 stenide och 3 korgide. Två dräktiga honbjörnar födde sina ungar i korgiden, ett idestyp som vanligtvis används av större hanar, inte av honor. Noterbart är att alla iden byggdes inom kärnområdena för björnarnas hemområden, snarare än vid periferin. En preliminär analys av SBBRP:s långsiktiga databas (1987-2024) visade på anmärkningsvärda trender. Ensamman hanbjörnar föredrog öppna grottor (32 %) jämfört med honor (12 %) och honor med ungar (13 %). Urgrävda iden var den vanligaste typen för alla björn kategorier och utgjorde 58-77 % av iden. Valet av iden har förändrats över åren, med ökat användande av öppna och naturliga iden, särskilt av honor med ungar. Om denna förändring beror på klimafförändringar, individuell beteende, mänsklig påverkan eller andra faktorer är ännu oklart och kommer att utforskas i framtida studier.

Expeditionen samlade också in tre spillningar från björnar efter vinterdvalan vid idena, som packades, märktes och frystes för framtida analys. Tecken på ungar, inklusive klättermärken, spillning och små dagbäddar, hittades vid fem iden. Habitatsområdet runt idena dominerades av äldre skogar, främst tall (52 %), följt av gran (27 %) och björk (21 %). Inget ide var belägen i fuktiga områden som myr eller våtmarker, och de flesta var belägna på sluttningar, medan endast några fanns på jämnt mark. Trädens genomsnittliga höjd runt iden var cirka 3 meter.

När det gäller spillningsinsamlingen hittade expeditionen 31 spillningar vid klusterplatser, och en klusterplats avslöjade rester från en vuxen älg som blivit dödad. En minskning av älgpopulationen i Sverige och studieområdet kunde vara orsaken. Tidigare års observationer, hittade rester från dödade älgar vid ungefär vart fjärde kluster. Expeditionen samlade in 100 % av de spillningsexempel som SBBRP normalt samlar under ett 10-dagars forskningsperiod.

Expeditionsdeltagarna bidrag ovärderliga för att hjälpa SBBRP att uppfylla sina datainsamlingsmål. Det kontinuerliga stödet från Biosphere Expeditions är avgörande för dessa långsiktiga forskningsprojekt, eftersom omfattande datamängder som samlas under många år krävs för att dra robusta vetenskapliga slutsatser.

På grund av den höga omsättningen av märkta björnar, särskilt på grund av jakt, står SBBRP inför utmaningar med att bibehålla ett tillräckligt antal GPS märkta björnar för forskningen. År 2024 minskade antalet märkta individer med 50 %, vilket gör att fångst av 20–40 nya björnar behövs. Att fånga och märka nya björnar är kostsamt, arbetsintensivt och komplicerat. Därför kommer nya metoder för att fånga björnar med hjälp av kamerafällor att utvecklas 2025, och arbetet med kamerafällorna blir en ny uppgift för expeditionendeltagare i 2025.

Sammanfattningsvis bidrog expeditionens resultat och det kontinuerliga stödet från Biosphere Expeditions avsevärt till SBBRP:s uppdrag att förstå brunbjörnens beteende och säkerställa bevarandet av dessa magnifika djur.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Friebe & Hammer (2020). The expedition has now been running for four years (2019, 2022, 2023, 2024, with an enforced COVID-19-related hiatus in 2020 and 2021) and assisted a long-term research project in Dalarna county in Sweden to help study and protect the local brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) population.

Details about the history, distribution and population dynamics of brown bears in Sweden and Norway, the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project, bear biology, detailed background to den site surveys as well as scat inventory surveys can be found in chapter 2.1. of Friebe & Hammer (2023).

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over a 10-day period and comprised a team of national and international citizen scientists, professional scientists and an expedition leader. Group dates were as shown in the team list below. Dates were chosen so that the expedition could visit the bear dens early in the season when tracks and signs were still fresh (bears usually leave their den sites from mid-April until the end of May).

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Dr. Andrea Friebe, the expedition leader was Roland Arnison. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

26 May – 4 June 2024: Maria Aragon (Spain), Almut Dold (Germany), Zoe Gilbert (UK), Maja Goschorska (Poland), Thomas Kampe (USA), Andreas Kappes (Germany), Silke Kutzer (Germany), Ben Rees (UK), Kari Velguth (USA), Louise Webb (assistant & chef).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place. The expedition leader tested positive for COVID-19 during setup and distanced himself from the rest of the team for much of the expedition and then re-joined towards the end. Nobody else contracted the disease.

1.3. Partners

Biosphere Expeditions' main partner on this expedition is [Björn & Vildmark](#) (Bears & Wilderness in Swedish), a company responsible for science communication, information and guided tours in the [Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project](#). Björn & Vildmark was established in 2001 with the purpose of distributing information about bear research and bear behaviour to the local population and managers. Dr. Andrea Friebe of Björn & Vildmark is also a researcher in the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project; the expedition followed the project's methodologies and shared its data with it.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as research assistants, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Thank you to all of you and the ones we have not managed to mention by name (you know who you are) for making it all happen. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support.

The expedition was embedded within the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project and we would like to thank the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), the Norwegian Environment Directorate, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency and the Swedish Association for Hunting and Wildlife Management for funding.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:
<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:
<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/sweden-2024/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.
<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/sweden>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid towards expedition costs a contribution of €2,680 per person per 10-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special non-personal equipment, and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	21,452
 Expenditure	
Base camp and food includes all board & lodging, base camp services	5603
Vehicles and fuel includes fuel, wear & tear, car hire charges; also includes per km support payment from Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project	1,665
Equipment and hardware includes research materials & gear, etc.	144
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff & expenses	3,998
Administration includes registration fees, sundries, etc.	43
Team recruitment Sweden as estimated % of PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	9,768
 Income – Expenditure	 231
 Total percentage spent directly on project	 99%

2. Winter den sites and scat sampling of Scandinavian brown bears in Sweden

Andrea Friebe
Björn & Vildmark
Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project

2.1. Introduction & background

The Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) – History and current research

The Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project (SBBRP) is one of the world's longest-running brown bear research initiatives. The purpose of the SBBRP is to provide the management authorities in Norway and Sweden with a solid scientific foundation for the current and future management of bears. The SBBRP is funded by authorities in both countries. Over the past 40 years, the SBBRP has expanded alongside advances in scientific methods, greatly enhancing understanding of brown bear biology, ecology, and behaviour in Scandinavia. Early research in the 1980s and 1990s focused on basic bear biology, including population size, distribution, and general behaviour such as diet, hibernation and reproduction. As the Scandinavian bear population grew, new genetic techniques and citizen science programmes helped refine population estimates and track bear health and disease.

From the 2000s onward, research expanded to study bear movement, habitat use and the effects of human activities such as infrastructure and hunting on bear behaviour. Advances in DNA analysis also enabled the study of genetic bottlenecks, population connectivity and more accurate bear population assessments. The SBBRP also began collaborating with human medical researchers, using bears as models for studying metabolic and cardiovascular diseases, and developing safe handling techniques for large carnivores.

Today the SBBRP continues to contribute to brown bear conservation and management. Research now also focuses on individual variation in bear behaviour, climate change adaptation and the impact of environmental toxins. The SBBRP's work remains crucial for both bear conservation and human medical advancements.

Long-term research projects, while requiring data collection over many years, offer significant advantages. They enable a deeper understanding of processes and phenomena by capturing changes over time, leading to more comprehensive scientific insights. These studies reveal trends and patterns, helping to detect long-term impacts, such as those caused by climate change or human activities on ecosystems. Extended data analysis can also identify risks and opportunities early, supporting better management and conservation decisions. Additionally, long-term studies allow for the testing and validation of hypotheses over time, resulting in more reliable scientific conclusions.

Many samples and measurements from bears have been collected since the inception of the SBBRP. Samples and measurements from animals shot during bear hunts are also gathered and analysed, among other things, within the SBBRP. Additionally, the SBBRP has been collecting data on bear behaviour, reproduction, home range use, and mapping of winter dens for nearly 40 years. Since 2015, scat samples have been collected to provide

insights into bear seasonal diet. Since 2019, Biosphere Expeditions has made a significant contribution to both the winter den mapping and the scat sampling study.

The Swedish bear population – History and new trends

In the 19th century politics played a significant role in the decline of large carnivores such the brown bear. Both Sweden and Norway aimed to eradicate the species, offering large bounties to hunters. Between 1856 and 1893, 5,164 bears were killed in Norway and 2,605 in Sweden, leading to a rapid population decline, especially in Sweden, where the population was smaller. By the late 1800s, bears were nearly extinct, surviving only in remote northern areas.

Around the turn of the 20th century, the Swedish Hunters' Association and the Swedish Academy developed plans to save Sweden's bears from extinction. In 1893, Sweden abolished bounties and introduced conservation measures that halted the decline by 1930, leaving around 130 bears in four subpopulations. Norway, on the other hand, continued to allow local bounties until 1972, and by the 1980s, the bear was extirpated from the country. In 1942, Sweden's bear population reached 294, and hunting was reintroduced in 1943.

From 1943 to 1994, the bear population grew by about 1.5% per year. SBBRP estimates for 1994 were 650-700 bears in Sweden and 22-35 in Norway. By 2018, Sweden's population rebounded to around 2,800, while Norway's population remains small at about 140 bears as of 2020.

Figure 2.1a. Development of the brown bear population in Sweden. Estimated numbers of bears in different years, data from www.naturvardsverket.se.

Figure 2.1b. Map showing estimated bear population density in 2022 in Sweden. The darker the colour, the higher the density. (Sköld, M. and Åsbrink, J. 2023). Red rectangle = southern study site of the SBBRP = expedition study site.

Bear hunting regulations in Sweden and population growth

The bear is a protected species in Sweden and, like other large predators, may only be hunted under strictly controlled conditions. The decision regarding licensed hunting is made each year by the County Administrative Board based on recommendations by a delegation with decision-making authority from the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency. The number of animals that may be hunted (the hunting quota) is determined by the County Administrative Board in consultation with other relevant counties and is based, among other things, on inventory results, regional management plans, calculations of possible hunting quotas, population density, genetic status and more.

To regulate the number of bears and prevent damage to livestock and reindeer, protective and some licensed hunting can be conducted as directed by the County Administrative Board. Those planning to hunt bears must (1) abide by hunting and firearms regulations as stipulated in hunting and weapons legislation, (2) familiarise themselves with the County Administrative Board's decision for the county in which they intend to hunt and the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency's decision for the entire country, and (3) be aware of how many animals remain on the quota in their area.

Protective hunting of bears

The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency has delegated the authority to decide on protective hunting of bears to the County Administrative Boards across the country. Those Boards can decide on protective hunting when needed, year-round. The hunting period for a specific location is determined in the decision on protective hunting. Applications for protective hunting must be submitted to the County Administrative Board in the county where the hunting is to take place. Protective hunting may be granted to prevent and stop serious damage to reindeer, livestock and other property. The need for protective hunting is assessed on a case-by-case basis. In some cases, if a bear is considered a danger to public safety, the police can decide on euthanasia under Section 9 of the Hunting Act.

Licensed hunting of bears

The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency has delegated the authority to decide on licensed hunting of bears to the County Administrative Boards in the northern and central predator management areas, parts of the country where bear populations are dense. The licensed hunting season runs from 21 August to 15 October each year, or until the quota has been reached. In parts of Norrbotten, bear hunting is only allowed until 30 September.

Annual decisions on bear hunting, including the conditions for each area, can be found on the [County Administrative Board's website](#). The County Administrative Boards' decisions on licensed hunting are based on the direction set by regional management for the county. Licensed hunting must never be conducted in a way that lets the number of bears in a county or management area fall below the minimum level set by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency.

Statistics showing the number of animals killed during licensed hunting are available on [Rovbase](#), which lists county, year and cause of death. The statistics cover all known causes of mortality in Scandinavia and are based on data registered in Rovbase by the Norwegian Nature Inspectorate and County Governor in Norway, as well as the County Administrative Boards and the National Veterinary Institute in Sweden (Figure 2.1c)

From these data it is evident that bear hunting has increased significantly over the last three years (Figure 2.1c). The Swedish bear population grew in the 1990s and spread to areas where they had previously been exterminated from. For example, before 1990, no bears were shot in Gävleborg and Västernorrland counties. Hunting quotas increased yearly until 2010, when 293 bears were killed through licensed hunts and 25 more through damage control/protective hunts.

Figure 2.1c. Number of shot bears in Sweden through licenced hunting and damage control/protective hunting 1980-2024. From www.Rovbase.se 2024-12-11.

The most recent bear population estimate, from 2017, is 2,877 bears. That year, around 280 bears were shot, about 10% of the population. In 2020, 436 bears were legally shot, about 15% of the population. In the following years this increased to 2021: 575 (20%), 2022: 725 (25%) and 2023: 740 (30%). Bear hunting in 2024 (still ongoing at the time of writing) will probably lead to a reduction of 20% of the bear population.

In 2024 the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency determined new minimum levels for bears for each management area and county and estimated the number of the actual bear population (official decision of the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (NV) 2024; NV-02105-23. The decision is valid until 29 April 2029) (Table 2.1a).

Table 2.1a. Estimated actual bear population & minimum levels as set by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency.

County	Minimum bear number	Estimated actual bear population (year of population estimation)
Norrbottn	220	650 (2021)
Västerbotten	160	450 (2019)
Jämtland	370	1044 (2020)
Västernorrland	150	442 (2020)
Dalarna*	240	323 (2017)
Gävleborg*	250	598 (2022)
Värmland	10	15 (2022)
TOTAL	1400	2448** (2023)

*main study area of the SBBRP / **based on Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (VN) calculation

Effects and consequences of bear hunting for SBBRP research

The impact and consequences of the significant increase in bear hunting needs to be closely monitored, because doubling the hunting quotas could have serious, potentially critical, consequences for the bear population. This is partly because bears are generally sensitive to high hunting pressure, as they do not reach sexual maturity until three to four years of age and produce few offspring: on average only every 2.5 years. Additionally, it is nearly impossible to distinguish between male and female bears until after they have been killed. Females, however, are more valuable than males for reproduction. How quickly a population declines or recovers largely depends on the sex ratio and whether there are enough adult bears. When bears were placed under protection at the beginning of the 20th century, it took over 100 years for the population to recover. Conversely, it can quickly reach a critical state again, and recovery from such a point will take a long time once more.

SBBRP's research methodology involves tracking individual bears, primarily females and their cubs, from birth to death. Experience has shown that the SBBRP needs to have around 50 GPS/radio-collared bears by the end of the year, after the hunting season. This is in order to obtain statistically robust estimates of key population parameters, such as age at first reproduction, litter size, interval between litters and mortality rates for different sexes and age classes. Over the past 20 years, bear hunting in Sweden has been high, around 10% of the population nationwide, approximately 300 bears annually, but with significant local variation (see www.rovbase.se). Lately, the SBBRP has therefore needed to start the field season with up to 70 radio-collared bears to ensure there are at least 50 radio-collared bears left by the end of the year, as bears are hunted and may also leave the population for other reasons, such as dispersal during sexual maturity.

Active bear population management of relatively small populations with specific management goals in limited areas requires detailed knowledge of bear ecology, demography and movement patterns. The SBBRP tracks changes in the bear population related to changes in their habitat (management changes, land use and climate). Bear population changes take time, since the generation time of bears is around 10 years. The best method to study population changes in bears is to track females and mark their cubs, which are then monitored from birth to death. This provides continuous data on changes in population parameters for all age groups. The long-term nature of the project makes it possible to understand how habitat, climate and management changes affect the bear and its conservation. This knowledge is critical from a scientific standpoint, as well as highly sought after by management authorities. It is essential for the sustainable management and conservation of the species and must therefore be based on wild individuals in their natural environment. Given the high turnover of marked bears, mainly due to hunting (see green line in Figure 2.1d), the SBBRP needs to replace lost bears each year to maintain a marked population of sufficient size (see red line of Figure 2.1e, % new captures of the total captures). In 2024, the SBBRP monitored a maximum of 62 marked individuals, but by the end of the year, this number had been reduced by 50% due to hunting, collar failures and other factors. As a result, the SBBRP needs to capture 20–40 new bears to maintain the required quota of marked bears for research. However, finding and collaring new bears is very challenging and requires very high input of funds, effort and manual labour, especially when the bear population is low and when collared bears are shot frequently and need to be replaced continuously. How this will be financed and organised in the future is unclear.

An added complication is that bears with high fat reserves should not be captured on warm days, as this increases the risk of hyperthermia, thereby subjecting the animals to heightened physiological stress. This is why the SBBRP captures brown bears only in spring, when ambient temperatures are much lower compared to the autumn after the hunting season. This voluntary seasonal restriction for reasons of bear welfare results in the loss of substantial capture opportunities in an already stressed system. Given that a significant portion of the research focuses on hibernation behaviour and physiology, this restriction impacts dataset robustness and continuity, and potentially compromises accuracy and statistical power of findings.

Figure 2.1d. Estimated brown bear population and bears shot in Sweden (2013-2024). *Year 2024: Numbers up to Sept 2024 when bear hunting was still ongoing. Left axis: The grey bars show the estimated number of the total bear population in Sweden. The yellow bars show the number of bears shot in Sweden (sum of bears shot during licenced hunting (blue area) and protective hunting (orange area)). Right axis: The blue line shows the estimated % of the bear population shot. The green line shows the number bears marked by the SBBRP that were shot during hunting.

Figure 2.1.e. Number of SBBRP bear captures. Blue bars: total number of captured/recaptured bears per year. Red line: Percentage of newly captured bears. The more marked bears are shot, the more new individuals must be found and captured (new captures) in order to conduct well-founded research with statistical power.

2.2. Materials and methods

Bear biology and den site survey

More details about bear biology, detailed background to den site surveys as well as scat inventory surveys can be found in chapter 2.1. of Friebe & Hammer (2023) and in the field protocols of Appendix II and III.

In summary, the expedition assists the SBBRP with labour-intensive data gathering, which is well suited to citizen science involvement. In particular, the expedition concentrates on:

- investigating den sites where radio marked bears of the SBBRP have hibernated the previous winter
- finding and collecting scats at those den sites, as well as cluster sites (places where GPS collars show that bears have spent prolonged periods of time, often a resting, feeding or kill site).

These research activities lend themselves to citizen science data gathering and the data gleaned are a significant help to the SBBRP and its aims to elucidate denning behaviour and for future analysis about bear feeding ecology. This is important, because human disturbance often has a negative effect on bears such as den abandonment, stress, habitat loss or fragmentation of habitat including alterations in food availability, and reduced reproductive success. Information about den site selections and the bears' choice of food will be helpful for managers when making decisions for brown bear conservation. Climate change is also another important factor, which can alter food availability and type, and therefore this denning duration. The emerging causal chain seems to be shorter, less severe winters and through this better food availability, which results in reduced denning duration.

Study area and population

This study was conducted in the northern boreal forest zone in Dalarna and Gävleborg counties, south-central Sweden (~61°N, 15°E), which is the southern study area of the SBBRP. The area comprises about 13,000 km², is hilly, and is covered with coniferous forests with interspersed lakes and bogs. Altitudes range from 200 m in the southeast to 1,000 m in the west but are mostly (>90%) below the treeline, which is at about 750 m (Dahle and Swenson 2003). The forest is dominated by Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), and birches (*Betula pendula* and *Betula pubescens*). Ground vegetation includes a variety of species of mosses, lichens, grass, heather and berries. Bilberries (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and crowberries (*Empetrum nigrum* subsp. *hermaphroditum*) are the main autumn food resource of brown bears in this area (Opseth 1998).

The landscape is intersected by a dense network of logging tracks (0.7 km/km²) and a few high-traffic asphalted roads (0.14 km/km²) (Martin et al. 2010). The human population density is low and only a few small villages exist in the study area (Swenson et al. 1999). Snow cover lasts from the end of October until late April and mean daily temperatures range from -7 °C in January to 15 °C in July (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute).

The study area of the SBBRP (Figure 2.1b) is part of the southernmost core reproductive area for Scandinavian brown bears, with a population density of about 30 individuals per 1000 km² (Bellemain et al. 2005, Solberg et al. 2006, Kindberg et al. 2011). The brown bear is a game species and legal hunting is the single-most important cause of mortality for brown bears in Sweden (Bischof et al. 2009).

The annual brown bear hunt runs from 21 August until quotas are reached (for actual numbers see www.rovbase.se and introduction of this report), but stops no later than 15 October in order to protect hibernating bears from disturbance.

Training and field work of citizen scientists

The expedition team comprised nine citizen scientists as per chapter 1.2. and the expedition scientist (and lead author of this report), expedition leader and a cook.

Training (two days) and field work with sampling (seven days) was conducted as per Friebe & Hammer (2023).

Den types, categories and measurements

Detailed description of den types, measurements and other field work methods are as per Friebe & Hammer (2023) and Table 2.2a.

Table 2.2a. Summary of den characteristics.

Den type	How common?	Used by	Den category	Insulating factor	Protection against disturbance	Can be adjusted in space and fit
Anthill	v. common	♀ & ♂	excavated	best	high	yes
Soil	common	♀ & ♂	excavated	very good	high	yes
Anthill/soil	common	♀ & ♂	excavated	very good	high	yes
Rock	uncommon	♀ & ♂	natural	low-medium	medium	no
Basket	medium	Mainly large ♂	open	lowest	lowest	no
Uprooted tree	rare	♀ & ♂	open	low	low	no

2.3. Results

Dens

The expedition investigated 29 winter positions of 27 different bears from 26 May to 4 June 2024 (Appendix I). All positions investigated were first recorded during the winter 2023/2024, except for two den positions, one den was used the previous year 2022/2023 and one very old den which was used 2013/2014. Two bears shifted their dens at least once during the hibernation season. However, only one of the second dens was found. Two 1.5-year-old males shared a den. This is very unusual and had previously been observed just once for two 1.5-year-old females during the last 40 years by the SBBRP. At 27 out of the 29 positions identified, the expedition found actual bear dens. Den positions are shown in Figure 2.3a.

In total, the expedition investigated: 5 anthill dens, 8 soil dens, 6 anthill/soil dens, 5 rock dens, 3 basket dens, and no dens under an uprooted tree. Two pregnant females that gave birth to cubs during winter hibernated in basket dens. Normally basket dens are mainly used by large males. All dens were constructed inside, rather than at the periphery, of the home range.

Table 2.3a. Den type overview 2024.

Den type > Den occupied by	Anthill	Soil	Anthill/ soil	Rock	Basket	Uprooted tree	Total
Pregnant bear		1	1	2	2	0	6
Solitary bear	4	4	2	2	1	0	13
Female with cubs	1	3	2	1		0	7
Siblings			2*			0	2
Total	5	8	7	5	3	0	28

*2 bears in one den (this den is counted twice in this table)

Figure 2.3a. Map of the Orsa Finnmark study site. Large white dots = winter den positions. Small red dots = cluster positions where scats were found. The bold letters beside the positions are the ID numbers of the bears. The yellow dot is the location of the expedition base.

Preliminary overview of the large history data set 1987-2024

The SBBRP has collected data about brown bear hibernation sites since 1987. Detailed analysis of this long-term dataset on brown bear choice of den types will be done over the coming years by SBBRP graduates and PhD students. However, a preliminary overview of the dataset is given below to show several trends.

Only dens in which bears hibernated the entire winter were included in the dataset. Those used for only part of the winter were excluded. Bears were classified into different categories: (1) Solitary independent males, (2) solitary independent females and (3) females with cubs (pregnant females that gave birth to young during hibernation and females that hibernated together with cubs). Den types were classified into three different categories (see Table 2.2a): (1) excavated, (2) natural, (3) open.

Solitary male bears on average used more open dens (32%) than solitary females (12%) and females with cubs (13%). There was no difference in the use of den types among solitary females and females with cubs. In general, excavated dens were the most common den type in all bear categories (58-77%) (see Figure 2.3b).

Figure 2.3b. Use of den categories of bears in different reproductive categories and sex (in %).

Den type selection has changed during the years (Figure 2.3c). Use of open and natural dens has increased, especially for females with cubs. Whether this phenomenon is caused by climate change, individual behaviour, human impact or other factors, will be analysed in the future.

Figure 2.3c. Den categories by year and reproductive status and sex. The bars show the percentage use of excavated dens (blue bars = anthill dens, soil dens, anthill/soil dens); natural dens (orange bars = rock dens); open dens (black bars = basket dens, dens under uprooted trees). The yellow line shows the number of individuals (n) included in the dataset for each year.

Scats

The expedition found three first post-hibernation bear scats at the den sites. We examined the scats, packed and labelled them and stored them in a -20°C freezer for further analysis in the future. Signs of cubs (climbing marks, scats and small day beds) were found at five den sites.

Habitat

None of the dens were located in water-rich areas such as bogs or swamps. All bears selected their den sites in older forests and no dens were located in younger forest (average tree height about 3 m) or at clearcuts. Twenty dens were located on slopes, and seven dens on level ground.

Figure 2.3d. Dens located on level ground (left) and on a slope (right).

The habitat in a radius of 50 m around the dens was dominated by Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* 52%) followed by spruce (*Picea abies* 27%) and birches (*Betula pendula* & *pubescens* 21%). At 10 m radius around the den, the tree species composition was similar. Birch trees represented 17%, spruce 26% and pine 57% of tree species.

Scat sampling at cluster sites

The expedition found 31 scats at cluster positions. At one cluster site the expedition found remains of a kill (adult moose). In previous years, the expedition group found kill remains of adult moose or moose calves at about every fourth cluster (25% in 2019, 24% in 2022 and 24% in 2023).

The expedition collected 100% of scat samples that the SBBRP normally collects during a whole year during its intensive 10-day research period. Previous expeditions collected 50% (2019) and 100% (2022 and 2023) (Fig 2.4a).

2.4. Discussion

Dens

The level of protection and insulation provided by a den is influenced by its structural type, which impacts heat retention and susceptibility to disturbances. Enclosed dens, particularly excavated ones, provide superior insulation by trapping both radiant heat from the soil and metabolic heat from the bear, maintaining a warmer internal temperature relative to ambient conditions. Older bears tend to excavate dens that are better suited to their body size, optimising thermal efficiency. Bedding materials such as moss and grass enhance insulation by creating a microclimate between the bear and the ground.

Male bears frequently select basket dens, while females prefer excavated anthill dens, which are associated with higher reproductive success due to better energy conservation during gestation and lactation. The decline in anthill availability, likely driven by intensive clear-cut forestry practices, may reduce the use of anthill dens. Such forestry practices result in monospecific, even-aged pine stands that lack the complexity of natural forests, negatively impacting keystone species like mound-living ants, which in turn affects denning sites.

Long-term studies are necessary to assess the impact of forestry and climate change on denning behaviour and reproductive success. Notably, recent observations of females giving birth in less insulated basket dens suggest possible climate-related shifts in denning strategies. Further research should investigate whether den type or habitat influences den abandonment rates and offspring body condition.

Here we concentrate on the results of the expeditions and how they add value to the larger SBBRP, for which the lead author works full-time.

2024 was the fourth year of citizen scientists assisting the SBBRP after 2019 (followed by an enforced COVID-19-related break in 2020 and 2021) and 2022-2023. 2023 was the first year when field sampling was extended by two days to a total expedition length of ten days.

The expedition visited 29 winter positions and investigated 27 dens, which represents about 61% of all winter positions that the SBBRP recorded in 2023. Previous expeditions investigated 34% (2019), 50% (2022) and 75% (2023) of all winter positions recorded (Fig 2.4a). The significant 2023 expedition increase is due to the extra two field days introduced with this expedition. The decline in 2024 of investigated dens was mainly due to the locations of the bear dens. Many dens were far from roads and were more difficult to access, but it also took longer time to drive to the dens, because many bears that had their home ranges close to the expedition base had been shot during the bear hunting season.

Figure 2.4a. Winter positions and scat samples results of the expeditions 2019, 2022, 2023 and 2024 (COVID hiatus in 2020).

Scats

The fact that the expedition found only one set of kill remains at cluster positions might be an indicator of the decreasing moose population in Sweden and in our study area (see www.viltdata.se). The fact that the expedition in 2024 once again collected 100% of all annual SBBRP scat samples is testament to the power and utility of citizen science in professional research projects.

Having said this, scat collection will cease for the 2025 expedition, because no funds are currently available to continue the scat sampling study, which began in 2015. This is because the SBBRP is facing enormous costs and a high workload to capture new bears due to the significant losses of marked bears during the bear hunt described above. This is a great scientific loss to the project. All scats collected and frozen up to 2024 will, however, be analysed and evaluated as planned in 2025.

Value of citizen science

Based on the data collected, it is evident that the citizen scientists involved in the expedition made a substantial contribution to the fieldwork of the SBBRP. We extend our gratitude to all participants and to Biosphere Expeditions for their invaluable assistance and dedication. The SBBRP deeply appreciates the support provided by Biosphere Expeditions in facilitating the collection of critical data for these long-term studies. Robust scientific conclusions require the accumulation of extensive datasets over many years. This necessity underscores the exceptional value of Biosphere Expeditions' open-ended, year-on-year support, which stands in contrast to many short-term grants typically spanning only a few years.

Based on the data collected, amongst others by Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists, the following reports and publications are expected to be completed and released within the next two years:

1. A global review of the factors influencing den types of brown bears: Throughout their range, brown bears show a wide range of den types used for hibernation. The forthcoming publication will review the literature with data throughout bears' range to document the types of dens that are used, and investigate whether factors of geology, landform or the presence of large anthills influence these choices. For example, it seems that cave-denning bears are most common in karst areas. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used to examine whether factors such as landform, geology, presence of permafrost, presence of large anthills by study area, etc. affect the den type used by brown bears. This will elucidate which den types brown bears prefer, when they have the choice.
2. Dietary specialisation in brown bears based on faecal samples (new Masters thesis in 2025): Scat data collected by Biosphere Expeditions will contribute to this thesis.
3. Effect of den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success: The factors influencing the large-scale hibernation site selection of brown bears in central Sweden are relatively well-known. However, there is a lack of knowledge regarding how den type affects reproductive success and hibernation duration. The objective of this study is to determine the factors that influence the den type used by brown bears and the effects of the den type on hibernation duration and reproductive success. Denning data from Biosphere Expeditions / the SBBRP will be used in this study. Appendix III gives a preview of some first preliminary results from a PhD study on this topic.

Given all of the above, the 2025 expedition will continue to:

- investigate den sites of brown bears to document effects of climate change and human activity on brown bear den site selection
- document signs of cubs at den sites to elucidate brown bear reproduction parameters, such as age of primiparity, cub survival and reproduction rates
- help the project to search for GPS collars that have fallen off bears in the woods
- help the project to find remains of dead bears to elucidate reasons of death such as illegal or intraspecific killing

In addition, the 2025 expedition will:

- help the project to test a new model of VHF-ear tags and compare their range with other VHF tags that have been used in the project.
- help to find missing bears by radio telemetry (bears with malfunction of their GPS collars, but which also have external VHF-transmitters on them, which can be used to locate the animals through manual triangulation).
- assist the project in setting, maintaining, baiting and monitoring camera traps and documenting bear camera trap captures.

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Appendix I: Details of bears and bear dens investigated by the expedition of the hibernation season 2023/24. The reproductive status shows if the bear hibernated alone (solitary), gave birth to cubs during hibernation in the den (pregnant), or hibernated together with dependent offspring (with offspring).

ID #	Bear name	Den #	Sex	Year bear born	Reproductive status	Den category	Den type	Den used all winter
W1803	SNYVLA	1	F	2017	pregnant	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W2309	VIDA	1	F	2022	solitary	excavated	Anthill	no
W9403	GRIVLA	1	F	1993	pregnant	natural	Rock	yes
W1509	SKÄRJÄMNA	1	F	2014	solitary	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W1319	SNYGGA	1	F	2012	with offspring	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W2322	GRÖNLOKE	1	M	2022	with sibling	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W2323	ULV	1	M	2022	with sibling	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W2326	KUSKA	2	F	2022	solitary	excavated	Soil	no
W0605	SÄLGA	1	F	2005	with offspring	excavated	Anthill	yes
W1909	DÖVA	1	F	2018	solitary	open	Basket	yes
W2012	LOVA	1	F	2019	solitary	excavated	Soil	yes
W1813	GUTMYRA	1	F	2017	with offspring	excavated	Soil	yes
W2019	NISSJA	1	F	adult	pregnant	open	Basket	yes
W2215	TICKA	1	F	2021	solitary	natural	Rock	yes
W2205	FLYTA	1	F	2021	pregnant	natural	Rock	yes
W2315	AGNETA	1	F	adult	pregnant	excavated	Soil	yes
W2204	LOMMI	1	F	adult	with offspring	excavated	Soil	yes
W2110	MUSÖRA	1	F	2020	solitary	excavated	Soil	yes
W2326	KUSKA	1	F	2022	solitary	excavated	Soil	no
W1203	PENGEL	1	F	2011	with offspring	excavated	Soil	yes
W2308	BENGT	1	M	2022	solitary	excavated	Anthill	no
W2310	TANSA	1	F	2310	solitary	excavated	Anthill	yes
W1708	LETTO	1	F	2016	with offspring	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W1304	BERGSLOGA	1	F	2012	pregnant	open	Basket	yes
W2325	HONKA	1	F	2022	solitary	excavated	Anthill	no
W2016	GANGSA	1	F	adult	solitary	excavated	Anthill/Soil	yes
W1815	OTTALA	1	F	2017	with offspring	natural	Rock	yes
W2312	NIFLA	1	F	adult	solitary	natural	Rock	yes

Appendix II: Den mapping protocol

BEAR DEN Protocol		OBSERVER DENS_2024_	YEAR (YYYY) MONTH (MM) DAY (DD) 2024 - - - -	
Related to		PROTOCOL ID: DENS_W ()		
LOCATION INFO AND YEAR DEN WAS USED	COORDINATES (GPS) (N/E) _____ / _____		DEN WAS USED WINTER <input type="checkbox"/> YEAR UNCERTAIN _____ / _____ <input type="checkbox"/> YEAR EXACT	
DEN WAS USED	<input type="checkbox"/> ALL OF WINTER	<input type="checkbox"/> PART OF WINTER FROM _____ TO _____	<input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN	<input type="checkbox"/> DEN USED IN PREVIOUS YEAR (S) BY BEAR WITH ID-no.: _____ YEAR(S) _____ / _____
POTENTIAL "DISTURBANCES" DURING USE OF DEN	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> CAPTURE <input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER (PROVIDE COMMENT)	COMMENT:		BEAR LEFT DEN AFTER <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN DISTURBANCE:
BEAR IDENTITY	DEN WAS USED BY: <input type="checkbox"/> UNMARKED BEAR <input type="checkbox"/> MARKED BEAR ID-NO.: _____		NAME:	SEX:
DEN'S POSITION IN THE TERRAIN WITHIN A 50 M RADIUS AND INCLINE OF TERRAIN	<input type="checkbox"/> MOUNTAIN (ABOVE TREELINE) <input type="checkbox"/> DECIDUOUS FOREST <input type="checkbox"/> Evergreen FOREST <input type="checkbox"/> YOUNG FOREST (AVERAGE ~3M) <input type="checkbox"/> CLEAR-CUT (LOWER THAN 1M) <input type="checkbox"/> MOUNTAIN SIDE <input type="checkbox"/> RAVINE <input type="checkbox"/> CLIFF EDGE <input type="checkbox"/> SLOPE <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____ <input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL GROUND <input type="checkbox"/> DEPRESSION <input type="checkbox"/> RIDGE _____ BEARING (360 DEGREES): _____ INCLINE (DEGREES): _____			
VEGETATION WITHIN 50M RADIUS IN PERCENT	TREES TALLER THAN 1M: (SUM OF ALL TREES EQUALS 100%, WRITE A ZERO FOR TREE SPECIES THAT ARE ABSENT) BIRCH: _____ % SPRUCE: _____ % PINE: _____ % OTHER TREE SPP.: _____ %, _____ %, _____ % (PROVIDE SPECIES NAME)			
NO. OF TREES TALLER THAN 3M WITHIN 10M RADIUS	(NB: NUMBER! NOT %, WRITE A ZERO FOR SPECIES WHERE NO TREES ARE PRESENT) BIRCH: _____ SPRUCE: _____ PINE: _____ OTHER TREE SPP.: _____, _____, _____ (PROVIDE SPECIES NAME)			
Relascope:	TreeHT (m) BIRCH: _____ SPRUCE: _____ PINE: _____			
	Number of trees (Nr of tree stems that fell outside the relascope gap (360°) . Tree stems smaller than the gap are NOT counted) BIRCH: _____ SPRUCE: _____ PINE: _____			
BEAR SCATS WITHIN 10M RADIUS	FIRST SCATS <input type="checkbox"/> ___ COLLECTED <input type="checkbox"/> ___ FOUND <input type="checkbox"/> ___ FOUND		SPRING SCATS <input type="checkbox"/> ___ COLLECTED <input type="checkbox"/> ___ FOUND IF CUBS ARE PRESENT: CUB SCATS <input type="checkbox"/> ___ COLLECTED <input type="checkbox"/> ___ FOUND	
BEAR SIGNS WITHIN 10M RADIUS	SIGNIS OF CUBS? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO			
	NR OF DENS: _____ NR OF DAYBEDS: _____	CLIMBINGMARKS NR OF TREES: FROM ADULTS: _____ FROM CUBS: _____	OTHER SIGNS (FOODS): DIGGED ANTHILLS: _____ TURNED STONES: _____ BROKEN TREESTUMPS: _____ OTHER (SPECIFY): _____	
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION				

TYPE OF DEN	<input type="checkbox"/> ANT HILL MIN. 80% ANT-HILL MATERIAL <input type="checkbox"/> ROCK DEN <input type="checkbox"/> NEST DEN <input type="checkbox"/> UPROOTED TREE								
	<input type="checkbox"/> SOIL DEN MIN 80% SOIL DEN <input type="checkbox"/> ANT HILL/SOIL DEN 20 - 80% ANT-HILL, REST SOIL MATERIALS <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____								
DEN ENTRANCE & PROPORTION OPEN AREA IN PERCENT	BEARING: DEGREES (360°)	NO. OF OPENINGS (>5 CM) PCS	PROP. OPEN AREA INCL. ENTRANCE %	DEN COLLAPSED : <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> YES _____ <input type="checkbox"/> BEFORE <input type="checkbox"/> EFTER <input type="checkbox"/> DURING DENNING <input type="checkbox"/> UNKNOWN					
CEILING & WALL CONSIST OF	<input type="checkbox"/> SOIL <input type="checkbox"/> ROCKS <input type="checkbox"/> TREE ROOTS > 5 CM <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER _____								
BED CONSISTS OF ADDS UP TO 100%	BERRY FOLIAGE %	MOSESSES %	BRANCHES %	HEATHER %	LICHENS %	GRASSES %	OTHER %	OTHER %	BED REMOVED FROM DEN? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO
DEN MEASUREMENTS									
1. OUTER LENGTH.....CM	OBS: CM !!!								
2. OUTER WIDTH.....CM									
3. OUTER HEIGHT.....CM									
4. ENTRANCE HEIGHT*.....CM									
5. ENTRANCE WIDTH*.....CM									
6. ENTRANCE LENGTH**.....CM									
7. INNER ENTRANCE HEIGHT.....CM									
8. INNER ENTRANCE WIDTH**.....CM									
9. INNER LENGTH.....CM									
10. INNER WIDTH.....CM									
11. INNER HEIGHT.....CM									
12. BED LENGTH.....CM									
13. BED WIDTH.....CM									
14. BED DEPTH.....CM									
15. BED THICKNESS.....CM									
16. THICKNESS OF WALLS AND ROOF.....CM.....CM.....CM (6 MEASUREMENTS).....CM.....CM.....CM									
*Maximum measurement for the bear, no cracks etc **when applicable									
PHOTO TAKEN	<input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO PICTURE NR 1 _____ PICTURE NR 2 _____ USE DIGITAL CAMERA (Ulefone) TO TAKE ONE PHOTO OF FRONT AND SIDE OF DEN. NOTE THE NUMBER OF YOU ULEPHONE (1,2 OR 3) AND NOTE THE LAST THREE DIGITS OF THE PHOTOFILE BELOW: (You do this by going Files > Camera > Select picture > then click (i) at the bottom.								
USE THIS SECTION TO DRAW A SCHEMATIC DRAWING OF THE DEN									

Denning Data Digest

2024

Dear Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists,

Since 1987, the Scandinavian Brown Bear Research Project has gathered valuable data on over 1,200 dens used by bears, thanks largely to your efforts. Your collaboration in the project, through field data collection, allows us to deepen our understanding of this species while also contributing to the training of tomorrow's scientists. **We are deeply grateful for your invaluable contributions!**

This digest provides an overview of some key statistics regarding the various types of dens used by bears. It also aims to introduce you to the research themes of one of our PhD students who is focusing on denning behavior.

Thank you once again, and happy reading!

The prevalence of den types varies across demographic groups

Each year, bears use new dens, which can take various forms. The five main types of dens observed in our study area are: natural rock cavities, ground dens excavated in the soil, ant hill dens created by digging into ant hills, ant hill-ground dens that are dug into both an ant hill and the ground, and nest dens, which are open-air dens made of materials piled around the spot where the bear sleeps.

Adult males exhibit different patterns of den use compared to other demographic groups. They use nest dens far more frequently than other bears. In contrast, subadult males show a prevalence of den types similar to that of females.

Trends in den use: rise of nest dens and decline of ant hill dens

Over the years, there has been an increase in nest dens and a decrease in the use of ant hill dens across all demographic groups, including females that enter dens during gestation and give birth over the winter.

Impact of den type on cub survival

Each year, after emerging from their dens, we observe the number of newborn cubs accompanying each mother. Litter sizes range from 1 to 4 cubs, but sometimes females lose all of their cubs during the winter, either during gestation or in the early weeks of life. Our observations suggest that using nest dens may increase the risk of cub loss.

A current PhD project on the importance of den type in the denning behaviour of brown bears

Baptiste Brault has started his PhD project on the effects of human and climatic disturbances on denning behavior and reproductive success in brown bears. His project includes data related to dens, and his objectives are as follows:

Chapter 1: Understanding how bears select their den sites and why certain types of dens are more frequently used than others. Baptiste will particularly investigate why there are changes in the use of den types over time.

Chapter 2: Determining the factors influencing den entry and exit dates. In this chapter, Baptiste will explore, among other things, whether the type of den used affects the duration of the denning period and the exit date.

Chapter 3: Identifying whether climate, human presence, and the type of den used can influence the risk of den abandonment during winter and litter size. Here, Baptiste will investigate whether the type of den used truly affects offspring survival.